

The relationship between management ability and investment opportunities with an emphasis on the role of political connection

Faramarz Nouri¹

¹ Faculty Member of Academic Center for Education, Culture and Research (ACECR), Tabriz, Iran

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p><i>Received: 15 November 2020</i> <i>Reviewed: 15 December 2020</i> <i>Revised: 31 December 2020</i> <i>Accept: 3 January 2021</i></p>	<p>Purpose: With the expansion of the quality level of activity as well as the widespread development of economic affairs, financial and investment decisions are among the most complex issues that arise in order to obtain the best return and desirability in the best conditions. In this regard, financial managers, given the primary responsibility for these decisions, seek to establish relationships between the factors of the firms in the firm, including investment opportunities. The purpose of this paper is to examine the relationship between management ability and political connection with investment opportunities. The QT ratio and market to book ratio (MTB) are used to measure corporate investment opportunities.</p> <p>Methodology: Corporate political connection is defined by Fasio's political cost variables and the use of the TOPSIS multi-criteria decision-making models and the Shannon entropy weighting method. In order to test the hypotheses, 116 companies listed in Tehran Stock Exchange during the period 2014-2019 were selected for the sample.</p> <p>Findings: The results of the analysis using the generalized least squares hybrid regression (GLS) method indicate that there is a significant and positive relationship between management ability and investment opportunities in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. There is a negative and significant relationship between political connection and investment opportunities. The political connection also does not affect the relationship between management ability and investment opportunities.</p> <p>Originality/Value: The purpose of this paper is to examine the relationship between management ability and political connection with investment opportunities. The QT ratio and market to book ratio (MTB) are used to measure corporate investment opportunities.</p>
<p>Keywords: <i>Management Ability, Investment Opportunities, Political Connection</i></p>	

¹ Corresponding Author: nory_faramarz@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

With the expansion of the quality level of activity as well as the extensive development of economic affairs, companies' financial decisions are among the complex issues that arise to achieve the best returns and utility in the best conditions. In this regard, financial managers, considering that the main responsibility for these decisions rests with them, seek to achieve relationships between the factors of the indicators in companies, including these issues of investment decisions [1].

In today's turbulent situation where companies and individuals are facing dramatic environmental and technological changes, achieving the desired level of performance is not easily possible. In this regard, the existence of a management system with appropriate capabilities and efficiency can lead to improving the performance of the organization in the current situation. Top managers better understand industry trends, accurately predict product demand, and invest more in high value-added projects [2]. Research on corporate financial behavior has also shown that managers with a good reputation may prefer high-risk projects that can hurt investment opportunities [3]. Many internal and external factors affect the performance of companies, one of which is the ability of managers to use resources. Capable managers may overstate their job growth and thereby worsen the company's future performance [4].

Studies show that political connection, through easy access to external resources and relationship-based contracts, provides valuable resources for businesses and influences managers' decisions and investments [5, 6]. On the other hand, managers of companies with political connections are forced to invest in unprofitable projects to achieve the social or political goals that the government is interested in, and thus the company's performance is weakened [7]. Having corporate political relationships can bring benefits such as favorable borrowing conditions, reduced financial costs, improved growth opportunities, and reduced the likelihood of bankruptcy [8, 9, 10]. However, political relations can have consequences such as high financial leverage, lower profitability, and profit-sharing, higher capital costs, and opportunistic exploitation of the rights of other shareholders [11, 12]. Given the diverse effects of management ability on investment decisions in different economic conditions, including corporate political relations with the government and the importance of investment opportunities, the main research question is:

How do the management ability and political connection affect investment opportunities?

2. Literature review

2.1. Investment Opportunities

Investment opportunities actually show the potential investment potential of the company. This means that the more the company can invest in the future, the more investment opportunities the company has [13]. The investment opportunities available to the company are one of the most important components of market value. A company's investment opportunities influence the way managers, owners, investors, and creditors view the company [14]. According to Jones and Sharma, investment opportunity represents the options for the growth or investment of the company [15]. Myers describes in his research the investment opportunity as a potentially profitable project that has not yet been realized and explains that the company can use it for economic profitability [16].

2.2. Management Ability

Management ability is one of the dimensions of corporate human capital that is classified as intangible assets. Demerjian et al., define management ability as the efficiency of managers compared to competitors in converting company resources into revenue. These sources of revenue generation in

companies include inventory costs, administrative and distribution costs, fixed assets, operating leases, R&D costs, and intangible assets of the company [17]. This is because capable managers take into account many of the facts that affect their predictions that others typically ignore. For example, in the case of forecasting the allowable amount of uncollectible receivables, weak managers pay attention only to the number of receivables burned in the past few years, while able managers calculate the historical rate of uncollectible receivables taking into account economic conditions, industry trends and changes in Adjust the needs of the company's customers [18]. Higher managerial ability can lead to more efficient management of the company's day-to-day operations, especially in critical periods of operations, where managerial decisions can have a significant impact on company performance. In addition, in times when the company is in crisis, more capable managers will make better decisions regarding the provision of the required resources [4]. More appropriate investment in more valuable projects and efficient staff management are also characteristics of capable managers. As a result, in the short term, more capable managers are expected to be able to earn more by using a certain level of resources, or by using fewer resources, to achieve a certain level of income [17]. Conversely, poor management decisions and poor leadership skills can lead a company to bankruptcy. Also, more capable managers have more knowledge and awareness about customers and macroeconomic conditions and can have a better understanding of more complex standards and implement them properly [18]. Studies such as Chemmanur et al., show that companies with more capable managers can access external financing on more favorable terms [19]. Also, because more capable managers can obtain more accurate information about investment opportunities, as a result, they will have better investments and will be more likely to achieve the desired result [20].

2.3. Management ability and investment opportunities

Bertrand and Schoar, have stated that managers with different styles, such as ability and experience, tend to adopt different strategies and policies when making operational decisions [21]. Koester et al., have stated that highly capable managers are more likely to avoid taxes, such as tax planning and revenue transfer [22]. Chemmanur et al., have shown that capable managers have a high ability to identify projects with high net present value (investment opportunities), so their investment will be greater [23]. Lin et al., have shown that the characteristics of executives such as professional background and level of education have a significant impact on the inputs and outputs of research and development companies [24]. Lee et al., have shown that companies with highly capable managers gain more economic benefits with high investment opportunities [2]. Therefore, policymakers and investors should pay more attention to the ability of managers. Management ability also plays an important role in corporate investment [25].

2.4. Political connection

The presence and influence of government officials in the corporate governance is a matter that can be taken for granted given the existence of empirical evidence. Businesses tend to have a closer relationship with the government because they are supported by the government. These relationships will bring many benefits such as tax breaks and easier access to credit. In relationship-based economic systems, the political connection is an important source of value for companies with relationships. Companies with political connections find it easier to access sources of capital and other benefits through their connections [26].

Moses, argues that as companies grow, their accountability increases, and corporate executives are exposed to accountability to a wide range of claimants. Some also believe that the larger the size of the

company, the more closely they are exposed to scrutiny [27]. On the other hand, large companies are a kind of implementers of government policies and are supported by the government because of their role. Therefore, it can be said that there is some kind of interaction between the government and large companies. In return for the implementation of its policies by large companies, the government has various advantages, including concluding profitable contracts, providing government currency, reducing customs tariffs, market access points, tax discounts, easier access to government subsidy credits, etc. These companies put. These companies also welcome this two-way interaction as they seek opportunities to grow or improve their current situation [28].

2.5. Political connection and investment opportunities

The activities of political managers are less transparent and managers hide political information from shareholders, so managers with political relations in the field of the investment may sacrifice the long-term returns of profitable projects for short-term returns [29]. Chaney et al., stated that due to the government's support for political connection, the operating environment in companies with political relations is not transparent, so the quality of the information in companies with a political information is lower than other companies. Hence, they invest in and finance unprofitable projects or high-risk projects that could harm the interests of shareholders as well as creditors [30]. In semi-complete markets, factors such as information asymmetry and agency problems may force managers to make inefficient investment decisions that lead to over-investment and under-investment [31].

2.6. Political Connection, Management Ability and Investment Opportunities

Empirical evidence from Chaney et al., has shown that the profits of companies with political connections are weaker than those without companies [30]. Because the benefits that companies with political connections derive from these relationships outweigh the costs they incur to have them. Managers of these companies may deliberately mislead investors by delaying reporting the benefits of political connections. In this case, the benefits of these connections are obtained at the expense of investors. Also, companies with political connections, compared to companies without this type of relationship, due to their political support, suffer less pressure from the capital market and the performance of political managers is more in line with the real goals and interests of these companies [32]. It is mainly subject to political, social, and individual goals. They believe that in companies with political connections, company managers and their abilities are neglected [30]. Therefore, it is expected that in companies with political connections, the motivation and ability of management to create investment opportunities and economic benefits for the company will be weakened.

Boubakri et al., examined the impact of political relations on firm performance and financing decisions. They found that companies with political affiliations had easier access to credit resources than other companies. In these companies, efforts are made to improve profitability through borrowing. Hence, political relations are strongly correlated with changes in leverage and operational performance [26]. Andreou et al., examined the relationship between management ability and firm performance. Research findings indicated that management ability is directly related to firm performance [4]. Siao and Chou, examined the effect of management ability on improving the level of cash writing. The results showed that the ability of management to keep the level of cash for companies increases investment opportunities. Also, companies with high management ability can use the company's cash in the best investment opportunities and improve the company's performance [33]. Demerjian et al., used accounting variables as a measure of management ability and concluded that management ability is directly related to firm performance [17]. Amore and Bennedsen, stated that corporate political

relationships increase operational efficiency even in the most corrupt environments [34]. Houston et al., showed that the cost of financing companies with political connections is much lower than other companies due to government support [35]. Saeed et al., examined the effect of political connection on company performance. Their results showed that there is a negative relationship between political connection and company performance. They found that the performance of political companies based on the indicators of return on assets and return on equity is about 17 and 15 percent lower than the performance of non-political companies, respectively [36]. Wang et al., examined the relationship between management ability, political connection, and fraudulent financial reporting in China. According to the findings, increasing the ability of management leads to a reduction in fraudulent financial reporting. Political connections in companies can also undermine the impact of management ability on the likelihood of financial statement fraud [37]. Andreou et al., examined the impact of management ability on corporate investment in times of crisis. The results showed that the ability of management can be effective in predicting next year's financial crisis [38]. Maaloul et al., examined the impact of political connection on the performance and value of Tunisian companies. Based on the results, political connection improves the performance and value of the company. In fact, investors tend to invest in companies with high political connections because of gaining more profits [39]. Wong and Hooy, have examined the impact of various political connections on company performance. The results indicate that among the political connections based on government-affiliated companies, board members, business people and members of the government family, communications through government-affiliated companies and board members have a positive and significant effect on the performance of companies. Political connection through business people and government family members is not meaningful and stable [40]. Lin et al., examined the impact of political connections and business groups on cash holdings among Chinese companies. The results showed that political connection was positively correlated with cash retention and business groups were negatively correlated with cash retention. Businesses with political affiliations also hold more cash [41]. Lee et al., in a study examined the relationship between management ability and investment opportunities. The results indicate that management ability has a positive and significant effect on investment opportunities [2]. Al-Gamrh et al., in a study indicate that investment opportunities have a negative influence on firm performance. The corporate governance index used here shows that the level of corporate governance practiced in the UAE is weak. strong corporate governance ameliorates the negative influence of investment opportunities, The sub-indices of corporate governance that matter the most for moderating investment opportunities are board functioning and ethics [42]. Sharma et al., indicate significant positive effects of political connections on Chinese firms' decisions to enter export markets and on their subsequent export performance [43]. Tee et al., in a study show that older politically connected firms, government-linked companies and firms connected through shareholders to important politicians have greater stock price crash risk. The management suppressing negative information from other shareholders differs according to different types of political connections [44]. Alshirah et al., in a study show that politically connected companies disclose less risk information than the unconnected ones in Jordan. The results also refer that family ownership contributes in mitigating the negative effect of the political connection on the level of corporate risk [45]. Nugrahanti, in a study show that political connection and board of commissioner size have a positive impact on Corporate Social Responsibility disclosures while independent board of commissioner and institutional ownership do not [46].

3. Data and Methodology

The research method is naturalistic in terms of approach and practical in terms of research purpose. In applied research, the purpose of this research is to provide solutions to meet the needs and solve problems and stakeholders use the research results in decisions related to investment opportunities. Due to the fact that the data related to the financial statements of companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange are used for analysis, so the research method is small in terms of the type of research. In terms of cognition, descriptive (non-laboratory) correlation type due to the description and analysis of relationships between research variables including management ability, political connection, investment opportunities and other control variables, quasi-experimental (quasi-experimental) and post-event due to selection. The period from 2014 to 2019 is for the period of research and non-intervention and manipulation of independent variables of research. Research method in terms of type of reasoning, inductive and in terms of retrospective and time perspective, longitudinal-cross-sectional (combined) method, in terms of data collection, library (refer to books, articles and other documents related to the research topic To compile the section of theoretical foundations and research background) and document mining (review of information and data of financial statements of Tehran Stock Exchange companies) and in terms of data analysis method, statistical method (using linear regression with combined data to analyze and Data analysis and review of research hypotheses. The statistical population of this research is all companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange. In order to select the sample from the member companies of the statistical community, companies that meet the following conditions in the period 2014 to 2019 were selected by systematic elimination method. By imposing restrictions and eliminating companies whose market value was large or unreasonable stock, 116 companies were selected for the statistical sample. Also removed for industries where companies were less than ϵ in the statistical sample. The reason for eliminating these companies is due to measuring the variable of management ability, and considering that to obtain this variable after measuring the ability of the company, the amount of residual error due to regression is obtained at the level of each industry and for different years separately. Therefore, in order to reduce the measurement error of the management ability of this type of companies and industries, they have been removed from the statistical sample of the research. Finally, 696 company-year data were collected for the research period.

The conceptual model of the research according to the theoretical foundations and background of the studies is as follows.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of research

In this research, Q-Tobin ratio (QT) has been used to calculate the investment opportunities of companies.

$$QT = \frac{\text{Stock market value} + \text{The book value of all debts}}{\text{Book value of total assets}} \quad (1)$$

This ratio has been used to measure investment opportunities in the studies of Lee et al. (2018). Also, to strengthen and solidify the results, the ratio of market value to equity book (MTB) has been used as another indicator for investment opportunities. This variable has been used in various researches as investment opportunities.

$$MTB = \frac{\text{Equity market value}}{\text{Book value of equity}} \quad (2)$$

The model presented by Demerjian et al., is used to measure management ability. In order to measure the efficiency of the company, Demerjian et al., used the data envelopment analysis (DEA) model [17]. Their pattern is as follows:

$$\text{TotalEfficiency } \tau = \frac{\text{Saeles}}{\alpha_1 \text{GOGS}\tau + \alpha_2 \text{SGA}\&A\tau + \alpha_3 \text{NETPPE}\tau + \alpha_4 \text{INTAN}\tau} \quad (3)$$

In their model, SALES: total sales of company i in year t; COGS: price of goods sold by company i in year t; SG&A: Company's general, administrative and sales expenses in year t; NETPPE: Net Presumptive Net Assets of Company i in year t; And INTAN: The net intangible assets of Company i in year t and Total EFFICIENCY are the efficiency of the company's total resources.

Demerjian et al., in order to gain the management ability and control the inherent characteristics of the company have provided a model that is as follows [17]:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{TotalEfficiency } \tau & \\
&= \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{SIZE} + \alpha_2 \text{MARKET SHEAR} + \alpha_3 \text{FREE CASH FLOW INDICATOR} + \alpha_4 \text{AGE} \\
&+ \alpha_5 \text{FOREIN INDICATOR} + \epsilon
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

In this model, Epsilon indicates the extent of management ability.

- **Political connection (PCON):** In this study, political companies are determined through TOPSIS multi-criteria decision-making patterns and Shannon entropy weighting. To separate political and non-political companies, Faccio, political cost variables will be used as follows [9]:
- **Stock market value:** The higher the stock market value, the greater the company's relationship with the stock exchange organization, which is under the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Finance.
- **Book value of assets:** The higher the book value of assets, the greater the company's relationship with the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Finance.
- **Income tax:** The higher the income tax, the more the company will have a relationship with the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Finance.
- **Number of employees:** The more employees, the greater the company's relationship with the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs.
- **Total Export Sales:** The higher the total export sales, the greater the company's relationship with the Ministry of Commerce.
- **Return on assets:** This variable is measured by the distribution of pre-tax profit to total assets. They have found that companies with higher rates of return on assets invest more. Therefore, the effect of this variable is controlled in the research [2].

In this study, to separate the impact of management ability and political connection on investment opportunities, the control variables of company size, financial leverage, cash holding and return on assets have been used:

To calculate the size of the company, the natural logarithm of the total book value of the company's assets at the end of the year will be used. Frank and Goyal, have stated in a study that firm size has a positive relationship with corporate investment [47]. Financial leverage is obtained by dividing total debt by total assets. Frank and Goyal, have stated that financial leverage is negatively related to investment and is a function of investment opportunities [47]. Cash hold is the level of cash hold that is equal to the ratio of cash to total assets of the company [2]. Simutin, states that companies that hold cash have plans for risky investment opportunities and invest more than other companies [48].

Research model to test the first hypothesis:

$$QT_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MA_{i,t} + \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_j \text{Control}_{j,i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t} \tag{5}$$

Research model to test the second hypothesis:

$$QT_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PCON_{i,t} + \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_j \text{Control}_{j,i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t} \tag{6}$$

Research model to test the third hypothesis:

$$QT_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MA_{i,t} + \beta_2 PCON_{i,t} + \beta_3 MA_{i,t} * PCON_{i,t} + \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_j Control_{j,i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (7)$$

To test the hypotheses and test the hypotheses, another criterion, the ratio of market value to book value of equity (MTB), is used to measure investment opportunities.

Multiple regression with panel data (combined) was used to test the research hypotheses. Multi-criteria decision making (MADM) methods are used to calculate the values of companies' political connection variables and data envelopment analysis (DEA) statistical technique is used for the company's ability variables. Data analysis was performed in GAMS, EXCEL and EVIEWS software.

Corporate political connection was calculated and measured using Shannon entropy and TOPSIS multi-criteria decision-making techniques. The final weight for political connection. In the next step, the company's ability was calculated based on data envelopment analysis method and using regression in SPSS software at the industry level and different years for companies, the remaining amount of errors was calculated and defined as management ability. In the next section, linear regression was performed for all research models using various tests of classical hypotheses, and finally the research hypotheses were analyzed by statistical tests in EVIEWS software.

4. Descriptive statistics

The following table shows the descriptive statistics of research variables. The amount of skewness of the variables is positive except for the financial leverage, so the distribution of the chart is skewed to the right. The elongation of the variables is positive and more than 3, which indicates a high elongation of the normal distribution. The level of significance obtained from the Jarquio-normality test is equal to zero and less than 5%, so the distribution of all variables is not normal. Table (1) shows the correlation between the variables. The correlation between management ability and investment opportunities is 0.1961, political connection and investment opportunities are negative 0.1650 and between the interaction of management ability and political connection with investment opportunities is negative 0.0247. Also, the correlation between all variables is less than 0.5 and therefore there is no problem in terms of alignment between the explanatory variables.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of research variables

variable	QT	SIZE	MTB	ROA	LEV	CASH	MEFFICENCY
Mean	2.049	6.377	3.442	0.137	0.535	0.071	0.000
Median	1.768	6.271	2.881	0.108	0.548	0.038	-0.047
Maximum	7.442	8.587	12.817	0.638	0.942	0.545	0.868
Minimum	0.727	4.845	0.608	-0.167	0.012	0.000	-0.494
Std. Dev.	0.976	0.631	2.076	0.132	0.198	0.091	0.235
Skewness	1.801	0.810	1.444	1.068	-0.358	2.502	0.856
Kurtosis	7.290	3.872	5.393	4.201	2.487	10.088	3.573
Jarque-Bera	910.35	98.23	408.26	174.15	22.49	2183.8	94.60
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Table 2. Correlation between research variables

Correlation	QT	MEFFICENCY	SIZE	ROA	LEV	CASH	PCONMEFFICENCY	PCON
QT	1	0.196	0.211	0.103	-0.123	0.319	-0.247	-0.165
MEFFICENCY		1	0.120	0.172	-0.193	0.161	0.371	-0.141
SIZE			1	0.145	-0.021	-0.001	0.157	0.174
ROA				1	-0.241	-0.124	0.179	-0.083
LEV					1	-0.164	-0.087	-0.133
CASH						1	0.182	0.089
PCONMEFFICENCY							1	-0.107
PCON								1

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between management ability and investment opportunities.

In order to test this hypothesis, the results of model estimation in the table below have been used. The probability value of F statistic is 0.000 and because this value is less than 5%, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 95% confidence level. Watson's camera statistic is 1.61, which indicates no autocorrelation. Also, the adjusted coefficient of determination shows that 52% of the changes of the dependent variable are explained by the independent and control variables of the model. In general, the results show that the coefficient of variable management ability (MEFFICENCY) is positive equal to 0.471, which shows a positive relationship between management ability and investment opportunities with the cytoxin index, which according to t-statistic and a significant value of 0.0001 variable coefficient. Management ability, the first hypothesis of the research is confirmed. That is, there is a significant relationship between management ability and investment opportunities in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. In other words, the greater the management ability, the more investment opportunities there are in companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange. This conclusion confirms the first hypothesis of the research at a significance level of 1%. Also, the variables of company size, rate of return on assets and cash holding have a positive and significant relationship with investment opportunities in Tehran Stock Exchange companies at a significant level of 1%. The relationship between financial leverage and investment opportunities is not significant. In fact, the higher the size of the company, the higher the rate of return on assets and the holding of cash, the more investment opportunities there are in companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange.

Table 3. Combined regression test for the first hypothesis with QT criterion

$QT_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MEFFICENCY_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 ROA_{i,t} + \beta_4 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_5 CASH_{i,t} + \varepsilon_0$				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MEFFICENCY	0.471	0.122	3.831	0.0001
SIZE	0.557	0.143	3.876	0.0001
ROA	0.981	0.279	3.512	0.0005
LEV	0.330	0.245	1.343	0.1795
CASH	1.578	0.320	4.928	0.0000
C	-1.579	0.950	-1.661	0.0972
R-squared	0.602			
Adjusted R-squared	0.519			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.605			
F-statistic	7.263			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000			

Hypothesis 2: There is a relationship between political connections and investment opportunities.

In order to test this hypothesis, the results of model estimation in the table below have been used. The probability value of F statistic is 0.000 and because this value is less than 5%, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 95% confidence level. Watson's camera statistic is 1.67, which indicates no autocorrelation. The adjusted coefficient of determination also shows that 54% of the changes of the dependent variable are explained by the independent and control variables of the model. In general, the results show that the coefficient of political connection (PCON) is negative 0.618, which indicates the negative relationship between political connection and investment opportunities with the cytobin index, which according to the t-statistic and a significant value of 0.000 coefficient of variable Political connection, the second hypothesis of the research is confirmed. That is, there is a significant relationship between political connections and investment opportunities in stock exchange companies. In other words, the more political connections there are, the less investment opportunities there are in companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange. Hence, the second hypothesis of the research is confirmed at a significance level of 1%. Also, the variables of firm size, rate of return on assets and holding cash have a significant relationship with investment opportunities.

Table 4. Combined regression test for the second hypothesis with QT criterion

$QT_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PCON_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 ROA_{i,t} + \beta_4 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_5 CASH_{i,t} + \varepsilon_0$				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
PCON	-0.618	0.0920	-6.693	0.0000
SIZE	0.699	0.144	4.853	0.0000
ROA	0.686	0.276	2.483	0.0133
LEV	0.363	0.258	1.404	0.1607
CASH	1.631	0.309	5.266	0.0000
C	-2.738	.937	-2.921	0.0036
R-squared	0.619			
Adjusted R-squared	0.450			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.668			
F-statistic	7.812			
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0000			

Hypothesis 3: Political connection affects the relationship between management ability and investment opportunities.

In order to test this hypothesis, the results of model estimation in the table below have been used. The probability value of F statistic is 0.000 and because this value is less than 5%, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 95% confidence level. Watson's camera statistic is 1.69, which indicates no autocorrelation. Also, the adjusted coefficient of determination shows that 53% of the changes of the dependent variable are explained by the independent and control variables of the model. In general, the results show that the coefficient of political connection * management ability (PCONMEFFICENCY) is negative 0.0532, which according to the t-statistic and a significant value of 0.818 can be said at a significant level of 5% political connection on the relationship between management ability. And investment opportunities are not affected by the Cytobin index. That is, political connection does not have a significant effect on the positive relationship between management ability and investment opportunities in stock exchange companies. In other words, corporate political relations with the government do not weaken the impact of management ability on increasing investment opportunities. Hence, the third hypothesis of the research is rejected. Also, the size of the company, the rate of return

on assets and the retention of cash in the third model of the research have a significant relationship with investment opportunities at the level of 99% confidence.

Table 5. Combined regression test for the third hypothesis with QT criterion

$$QT_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MEFFICENCY_{i,t} + \beta_2 PCON_{i,t} + \beta_3 MEFFICENCY_{i,t} * PCON_{i,t} + \beta_4 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_5 ROA_{i,t} + \beta_6 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_7 CASH_{i,t} + \varepsilon_0$$

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MEFFICENCY	0.444	0.169	2.627	0.0088
PCON	-0.586	0.097	-6.042	0.0000
PCONMEFFICENCY	-0.053	.232	-0.229	0.8189
SIZE	0.523	0.151	3.445	0.006
ROA	0.807	0.284	2.841	0.0046
LEV	0.386	0.264	1.459	0.1449
CASH	1.671	0.316	5.179	0.0000
C	-1.605	0.993	-1.616	0.1056
R-squared	0.619			
Adjusted R-squared	0.538			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.690			
F-statistic	7.642			
Prob (F-statistic)	0.000			

In order to test this hypothesis, the results of model estimation in the table below have been used. The probability value of F statistic is 0.000 and because this value is less than 5%, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 95% confidence level. Watson's camera statistic is 1.72, which indicates no autocorrelation. Also, the adjusted coefficient of determination shows that 53% of the changes of the dependent variable are explained by the independent and control variables of the model. In general, the results show that the coefficient of political connection * management ability (PCONMEFFICENCY) is negative 0.049, which according to t-statistic and a significant value of 0.932 can be said at a significant level of 5% political connection on the relationship between management ability. And investment opportunities are not affected by the MTB index. That is, political connection does not have a significant effect on the positive relationship between management ability and investment opportunities in stock exchange companies. In other words, corporate political relations with the government do not weaken the impact of management ability on increasing investment opportunities. Hence, the third hypothesis of the research is rejected with the market value index to the book value of equity. Also in the third model of financial leverage research, the rate of return on assets and cash retention has a significant relationship with investment opportunities at the 95% confidence level.

Table 6. Combined regression test for the third hypothesis with MTB criterion

$$MTB_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MEFFICENCY_{i,t} + \beta_2 PCON_{i,t} + \beta_3 MEFFICENCY_{i,t} * PCON_{i,t} + \beta_4 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_5 ROA_{i,t} + \beta_6 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_7 CASH_{i,t} + \varepsilon_0$$

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MEFFICENCY	1.081	0.498	2.167	0.0306
PCON	-1.292	0.219	-5.885	0.0000
PCONMEFFICENCY	-0.049	0.584	-0.084	0.9326
SIZE	0.508	0.351	1.445	0.1490
ROA	1.098	0.543	2.019	0.0439
LEV	4.702	0.549	8.561	0.0000
CASH	3.735	0.690	5.408	0.0000
C	-3.379	2.366	-1.427	0.1539
R-squared	0.613			
Adjusted R-squared	0.531			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.727			
F-statistic	7.459			
Prob (F-statistic)	0.000			

Table (7) summarizes the results of testing the research hypotheses. According to the combined regression tests with fixed effects at a significance level of 1%, the first and second hypotheses are confirmed. The third hypothesis is rejected at a significance level of 5%.

Table 7. Summary of the results of research hypotheses

Hypothesis title	Type of regression	The result of the hypothesis
There is a connection between management ability and investment opportunities.	Combined regression - fixed effects Generalized least squares method	Confirmed at a significance level of 1%.
There is a connection between political connections and investment opportunities.	Combined regression - fixed effects Generalized least squares method	Confirmed at a significance level of 1%.
Political connections affect the relationship between management ability and investment opportunities.	Combined regression - fixed effects Generalized least squares method	At a significant level of 5 %is rejected.

5. Conclusion

The results of testing the first hypothesis of the research show that there is a significant and positive relationship between management ability and investment opportunities at a significant level of 1% in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. In other words, the greater the management ability in the company, the more investment opportunities there are in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. The results of this study are consistent with the study of Chemmanur et al. [23]. They have shown that capable managers have a great ability to identify projects with high net present value (investment opportunities), so their investment will be higher. . The results of the study are also consistent with the study of Lee et al. [2]. They stated that companies with highly capable managers gain more economic benefits with high investment opportunities. Therefore, policymakers and investors should pay more attention to the ability of managers. Management ability also plays an important role in corporate investment. The results of the first hypothesis are consistent with the study of Siao and Chou, who state that the ability of management to keep cash levels high for companies increases investment opportunities [33]. Also, companies with high management ability can use the company's cash in the best investment opportunities and improve the company's performance. In general, it is argued that capable managers have more knowledge and analytical understanding of the current and future conditions of the company, industry trends and macroeconomic situation, and can make more accurate and effective judgments and estimates and perform better for the company. To bring. Therefore, the empowerment of managers leads to increased investment opportunities and economic benefits for companies.

The results of testing the second hypothesis of the research show that there is a significant and negative relationship between political connection and investment opportunities at a significant level of 1% in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. In other words, the more political relations the company has with the government, the less investment opportunities there are in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. Deng et al., stated that the activities of political managers are less transparent and managers hide political information from shareholders [29]. As a result, managers with political relationships in the field of investment may sacrifice the long-term returns of profitable projects for short-term returns. The results of the second hypothesis are consistent with this study. The results of the study are consistent with the study of Chaney et al., who stated that due to government support for political connection, the operating

environment in companies with political relations is not transparent, thus the quality of information in companies with political information [30]. It is lower than other companies. Hence, they invest in and finance unprofitable projects or high-risk projects that could harm the interests of shareholders as well as creditors. The research findings are consistent with the results of the study of Saeed et al. [36]. They showed that there is a negative relationship between political connection and company performance. Pan and Tian, state that managers of companies with political connections are forced to invest in unprofitable projects to achieve the social or political goals that the government is interested in, thereby undermining the company's performance. The results of this hypothesis are consistent with the research of Pan and Tian [7]. It is argued that in companies with political relations with the government, in order to achieve social and political goals, managers invest in high-risk and undesirable projects without economic added value, and due to low transparency and quality of information in this type of company, investment opportunities are less.

The results of testing the third hypothesis of the research show that political connection does not affect the positive relationship between management ability and investment opportunities at a significant level of 5% in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. In other words, the political relations of companies with the government do not weaken the effect of management ability on increasing investment opportunities in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. Chaney et al., stated that due to the government's support for political connection, the operating environment in companies with political relations is not transparent, so the quality of information in companies with political information is lower than other companies [30]. Hence, they invest in and finance unprofitable projects or high-risk projects that could harm the interests of shareholders as well as creditors. In fact, the political relations that govern the company affect the motivation and ability of managers, and under conditions of information asymmetry and lack of transparency, companies invest too little or too much. The result of the third hypothesis of the research is not consistent with the findings of Chaney et al. [30], so that the relationship between management ability and investment opportunities has not been affected by companies' political relations with the government. The reason for rejecting the third hypothesis of the research can be argued that companies with political connections, with the support of government and powerful politicians, are not sensitive to the pressures and competition in the market by creating a monopoly space and provide the goods and services they need with the conditions. They provide adequate credit from the money market and the capital market, which facilitates and improves the activities and performance of these companies. Regardless of the advantages and disadvantages of political connection between companies and the government that have been mentioned in previous research, the results of the present study indicate that establishing political connection with the government can reduce investment opportunities to weaken managerial capacity. Do not lead to an increase in investment opportunities in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. According to the results of the research to the managers and stakeholders of companies, the following suggestions are made:

- 1- Companies should select capable managers to create value and improve investment opportunities for the company's management and by using them to provide the ground for investment efficiency.
- 2- Political connection has a negative effect on investment opportunities, so it is suggested that instead of employing people with more political relations, companies look for capable managers with appropriate characteristics such as mastery of management techniques, familiarity with industry and competitors.

3- The performance of managers in companies with political connections is mainly measured based on short-term criteria, so managers seek benefits in the short term and this will have a negative impact on the value of companies, so creating appropriate corporate governance mechanisms can reduce to some extent the negative effects of political connection on investment opportunities.

5- Considering the positive and significant relationship between management ability and investment opportunities, policy makers and regulators of contracts and regulations are recommended to design these bonus contracts and other items to increase investment opportunities. Companies use.

6- Using the results of the research that the ability of management can play a significant role in creating investment opportunities, capital market and economy of the country, it is suggested to the Stock Exchange Organization that companies be based on managerial ability and with Pay attention to their efficiency and performance index so that in addition to increasing the transparency of capital market information and creating a competitive environment between managers, investors and creditors can rely on this information to make better investment decisions.

Conflicts of Interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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